

FORMATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS' KNOWLEDGE, SKILLS, AND COMPETENCIES IN THE ELECTRONIC DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM (PTS) PLATFORM

Tojiboyev Jasurbek Zokirjon o'g'li

Researcher at the 3rd stage of the National Institute of Pedagogy named after Qori Niyoziy,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15094272>

Abstract. *Until now, the existing education system has prioritized teaching. However, in the current era of societal informatization, the use of digital technologies has gained significant importance, shifting the focus towards teaching how to learn. Therefore, it is necessary to replace the traditional teacher-textbook-student paradigm with a student-textbook-teacher paradigm. The shortcomings of previous works on teaching engineering computer graphics in higher education institutions, based on the method of comparing software programs, have been addressed.*

Keywords: "digital technology," "information communication," "information technology".

The general pedagogical challenge across all stages of education is to increase and enhance the interest and activity of learners. Therefore, in training pedagogical staff for the secondary specialized education system, it is essential to expand the opportunities for future vocational education teachers to use information and communication technologies (ICT) in the classroom. Thus, all future vocational education teachers must possess the skills to effectively utilize the latest modern digital technologies.

Typically, software developers are responsible for creating educational tools. While these developers may have sufficient knowledge about the quality of the products they create, they often lack a deep understanding of teaching methodologies. This can result in educational software not fully meeting methodological requirements.

To improve the effectiveness of training qualified vocational education teachers based on modern information technologies, it is advisable to include specialized courses on digital technologies in the curricula of vocational education bachelor's programs. These courses can provide knowledge on implementing ICT-based teaching methods for each subject. Additionally, it is necessary to revise the curricula of teaching methodology courses in higher-level vocational education programs and incorporate topics on the application of modern digital technologies in teaching these subjects.

In higher education institutions, the course "Vocational Education Methodology" is taught to improve the professional training of future teachers in vocational education bachelor's programs. This course not only covers traditional teaching approaches but also develops the ability to apply advanced methods. However, this course does not sufficiently address the challenges of creating methodological and didactic materials.

In this regard, there is a need to train vocational education teachers who can either use existing software-based educational and methodological tools or create their own. To achieve this, it is appropriate to introduce the Professional Education System (PTS) platform into the electronic information education environment. This platform aims to develop future vocational education teachers' knowledge, skills, and competencies in pedagogical design, enabling them to meet state educational standards and effectively apply modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

Requirements for mastering the subject:

In the process of mastering the subject "Educational Technologies," students should:

- Understand individualized approaches to learners.
- Manage the education and upbringing process.

- Recognize the role and place of pedagogy in the education system.
- Apply scientific research methods in pedagogy and educational theory.
- Understand the upbringing and development of learners.
- Know the laws and principles of education and upbringing.
- Be familiar with the forms and methods of organizing education.
- Understand the history of vocational education development in Uzbekistan.
- Know the "Law on Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training."
- Understand the goals, content, and structure of continuous education.
- Be familiar with the main regulatory documents for organizing and managing secondary specialized vocational education.
- Understand the content of secondary specialized vocational education.
- Know the concepts of pedagogical skills and pedagogical knowledge.
- Understand the specifics of pedagogical activity, professional knowledge, and pedagogical abilities.
- Be familiar with pedagogical techniques and methods of their formation.
- Understand communication culture and the psychology of teaching.
- Analyze and implement pedagogical communication skills in the educational process.
- Understand educational technology.
- Know the advantages and applications of modern pedagogical technologies.
- Understand the main components and stages of the educational process.
- Improve the educational process.
- Have an understanding of digital technologies in the electronic information education environment (PTS).
- Understand the continuity and integrity of education.
- Know the goals and tasks of vocational education in secondary specialized vocational institutions.
- Understand vocational-pedagogical communication technology.
- Understand the process of teacher personality formation.
- Understand the specifics of pedagogical activity.
- Know methods for forming new knowledge, skills, and competencies.
- Optimize forms and methods in implementing pedagogical projects.
- Understand the elements of pedagogical technology in organizing the educational process.
- Apply active teaching methods.
- Understand the importance of assessment and correction in learning.
- Be able to use and apply electronic information education environments (PTS) in the educational process.
- Manage the educational process.
- Conduct pedagogical diagnostics with students.
- Apply widespread methods of education and upbringing.
- Organize educational events and implement new pedagogical technologies in the educational process.
- Activate students' activities.
- Apply pedagogical techniques and methods of their formation.
- Analyze and implement pedagogical experience.
- Apply technologies for solving pedagogical situations and problems.
- Use educational activity technologies in practice.
- Apply pedagogical technologies in the educational process.
- Use active teaching methods.
- Be skilled in designing pedagogical technologies for general vocational subjects using modern teaching tools and active methods.

Conclusion: The significant result of pedagogical design in vocational education processes is not only the creation of specific pedagogical projects but also the development of the teacher's

ability to accept innovations, express their perspective, critically evaluate their projects, and integrate pedagogical design as a necessary component of their professional activity. The objective complexity of pedagogical design in vocational education processes within the electronic information education environment must be considered in the design process, with special attention to methodological support. Practice has shown that pedagogical design in vocational education processes within the electronic information education environment depends on several factors, and the PTS platform plays a significant role in this regard. The integration of pedagogical and information-communication technologies, electronic educational resources, and technological approaches are among these factors.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "On the Development Strategy of the Higher Education System of Uzbekistan until 2030." PF-5847. October 8, 2019.
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "On Measures to Further Improve the Quality of Products and Expand the Participation of Industries in Ensuring Safety." PQ-3151. July 27, 2017.
3. Jokhova E.Yu. *Computer Technology for Solving Geometric Problems as a Means of Forming Conceptual Apparatus*. Dissertation. Yaroslavl State Pedagogical University, 1996.
4. Dammer M.D. *The Role of the Scientific Principle in Forming the Content of Education*. Bulletin of the South Ural State University. Series: Education. Pedagogical Sciences, 2012, No. 4(263).
5. Meretukova Z.K., Chinazirova A.R. *On the Didactic Principle of Scientificity and Scientific Worldview in the Context of the Post-Nonclassical Scientific Picture of the World*. Bulletin of the Adyghe State University. Series 3: Pedagogy and Psychology, 2007.
6. Chernobelskaya G.M. *Methods of Teaching Chemistry in Secondary Schools*. Textbook for Students of Higher Educational Institutions. Moscow: VLADOS, 2000.